

A STUDY ON CONSUMER SATISFACTION TOWARDS ORGANIC FOOD PRODUCTS WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO COIMBATORE CITY

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Abstract:

Availability of organic input and output is critical for improve of organic farming in the country. Development of efficient marketing system is the need of the hour for strengthening the organic production in India. This paper made a humble attempt to understanding the consumer perception about organic product and marketing in Coimbatore city. The results concluded that most of the consumer especially in urban people prefer organic food product. Marketing of organic product is so poor in study area so the demand for organic product is increases but supply is very low. The major reasons are organic producer are low, adequate market facility is not there, few number of shops, lack of awareness, and so on. Therefore if farmer as well as government give interest to organic farming easily enhancing good marketing system in Tamilnadu.

Key Words: Organic Products, Price, Attitude, Health Consciousness & Consumer Satisfaction.

1. Introduction:

Organic farm production and trade has emerged as an important sector in India As in other parts of the developing world, and is seen as an important strategy of facilitating sustainable development. The development of organic agriculture in India is receiving increasing attention among the farmer/ Producers, processors, trader, exporters and consumers. Over the past decade consumption patterns of consumer will be change especially in food consumption because all consumer to eat organic food because of the perception is to eat the organic food is good for health and it's grows with use of organic manual and use natural resource, so consumer behaviour will be shift to organic food item, and quality and safety in food attract consumer interest in organic food that is free from pesticides and chemical residues. Organic agriculture is produced with an objective to produce healthy and quality foods without using synthetic chemical products. Thus, organic agriculture not only preserves the environment but it also improves public health, bringing significant benefits both to the economy as well as to the social cohesion of rural areas. The interest of consumers and public institutions in organically produced foods has increased, mainly in developed countries, in response to consumers' concerns about food safety, human health and the environment. The organic food market has grown continuously over the past decade, but, the total share of organic food is still small compared with the total food market. Even in countries with matured organic sectors such as Switzerland, Austria and Denmark, organic food consumption is barely more than 5 per cent of total food consumption

2. Objectives:

- ✓ To study about the customer satisfaction towards organic products.
- ✓ To know about the factors influencing the customer to buy the product.
- ✓ To know the opinion of customers.
- ✓ To examine the source of an awareness.

3. Scope of the Study:

Organic food promotes a balance of human, other living organisms and the nature. It also promotes no artificial preservatives and best maintain the originality of food. This prevents excess use harmful ingredients and thereby ensures health. This study attempted to gain knowledge about consumer attitude towards organic food product consumption and to see whether there is any potential this might have for changing their behavior. The rationale for carrying out this study is that consideration for the environment could come only from well-informed citizens who are aware of, and fully committed to their rights to a quality health and environment. Nevertheless, before any behavior can be changed, it is necessary to evaluate the current state of consumers' awareness and knowledge. Therefore consumer's attitude, perception towards organic food products, willingness to pay for organic food product and intention to purchase organic food will be the main agenda of this study

4. Statement of the Problem:

The study is conducted to know the problem faced by the using non organic products which has chemical fertilizers input to get more yield of the products today the world requires new discussion and innovation which are leads to the potential buyers usage of harmful to the consumers have got awareness on organic products started buying and utilizing for their regular consumption the researcher shows interest on the positive impact to the society thus this particular study has been carried out.

5. Methodology of the Study:

Methodology refers to the study of methods from which we can obtain knowledge. It is one of the scientific ways of solving problems.

Area of the Study: The area of the study refers to Coimbatore city.

Sources of Data: The study used both primary data as well as secondary data. The data was collected from 100 consumers by questionnaire method.

Sample and Size: The study based on primary data. The primary data had collected from selected consumers on Simple Random sampling techniques and Retail outlets of Organic products, Organic Products Marketing Agencies.

Statistical Tools Used: Simple percentage analysis is used in the study for the purpose of analysis.

Tools for Analysis: The Following statistical tools were used in this study.

- ✓ Simple percentage Analysis
- ✓ Chi-square Analysis.
- ✓ Average ranking analysis.

6. Limitations of the Study:

- ✓ The study was conducted in and around Coimbatore area only. Hence the results may not be applicable to other geographical areas.
- ✓ The size of the sample is low when compared to the total population.
- ✓ The study was limited to extend of abilities and willingness of the respondents to answer appropriately to the questions.

7. Analysis and Interpretation of Data:

S.No	Source	Factors	No. of Respondents	%	Total
1	Gender	Male	31	31	100%
		Female	69	69	
2	Classification on Age Group	Below 20 years	24	24	100%
		21 to 30 years	36	36	
		31 to 40 years	19	19	
		Above 40 years	21	21	
3	Monthly Income	Below Rs 10000	18	18	100%
		Rs 10001 to 20000	32	32	
		Rs 20001 to 40000	32	32	
		Above RS. 40001	18	18	
4	Source of Awareness	Television	22	22	100%
		News paper	26	26	
		Magazine	15	15	
		Friends and relatives	37	37	
5	Type of Products	Fruits	17	17	100%
		Vegetables	70	70	
		Medicine	05	05	
		Grocery	05	05	
		Others	03	03	
6	Reason to Prefer the Product	Protect environment	28	28	100%
		Prefer taste	19	19	
		Ethical reason	07	07	
		Quality of product	17	17	
		Protect health	29	29	
7	Opinion About Usage of the Product	Good	26	26	100%
		Very good	44	44	
		Neutral	30	30	
		Bad	00	00	
		Very bad	00	00	
8	Satisfaction Level Towards Organic Products	Satisfied	39	39	100%
		Highly satisfied	21	21	
		Neutral	34	34	
		Dissatisfied	03	03	
		Highly dissatisfied	02	02	
9	Availability of the Product	Super market	43	43	100%
		Organic store	27	27	

		Producer	10	10	
		Other	20	20	
10	Purchasing Organic Product	Several time	16	16	100%
		Once in a week	58	58	
		Once in a month	20	20	
		Few times a year	06	06	

- ✓ Majority 69% of the respondents are female.
- ✓ Majority 36% of the respondents are their age group up to “21 to 30years”.
- ✓ Majority 64% of the respondents comes under employed category.
- ✓ Majority 37% of the respondents came to know the product through friends and relatives.
- ✓ Majority 70% of them are using vegetables.
- ✓ Majority 29% of the respondents prefer for protection health.
- ✓ Majority 44% of the respondents have good opinion regarding the organic products.
- ✓ Majority 39% of the respondents were satisfied with the organic products.
- ✓ Majority 43% of the respondents purchase organic food from super market.
- ✓ Among respondents 58% of the respondents purchase organic product once in a week.

8. Testing of Hypothesis:

Chi-Square Test:

H₀: there is no significant relationship between monthly income and type of organic products.

H₀: there is no significant relationship between gender and opinion of organic products.

Variables	Calculate Value	Degree of Freedom	Table Value	Accepted/ Rejected	Level of Significance
Monthly income and type of organic products.	14.23	12	21.0	Rejected	5%
GENDER and opinion of the organic product.	4.2	4	9.49	Rejected	5%

Interpretation:

The calculated value of chi-square is more than the table value at 5% level of significance. So the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence there is a relationship between monthly income and type of organic products.

The calculated value of chi-square is more than the table value at 5% level of significance. So the null hypothesis is rejected. Hence there is a relationship between gender and opinion of organic products.

9. Average Ranking Analysis:

Ranking Factors Influence to Choose Organic Food Products

Factors	Rank I	Rank II	Rank III	Rank IV	Rank V	Rank VI	Rank VII	Rank VIII	Rank IX	Total	Mean	Rank
	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1			
Quality	6	8	8	14	18	9	11	13	13	100	4.56	9
Score	54	64	56	84	90	36	33	26	13	456		
Quantity	10	8	15	10	10	12	12	12	11	100	4.88	7
Score	90	64	105	60	50	48	36	24	11	488		
Price	12	10	12	10	8	9	12	12	15	100	4.83	8
Score	108	80	84	60	40	36	36	24	15	483		
Availability	12	10	10	11	11	13	11	12	10	100	4.98	6
Score	108	80	70	66	55	52	33	24	10	498		
Taste of the Product	6	12	17	13	12	9	10	10	11	100	5.04	4
Score	54	96	119	78	60	36	30	20	11	504		
Health Maintenance	15	8	8	15	13	13	10	10	8	100	5.20	3
Score	135	64	56	90	65	52	30	20	8	520		
Package	9	12	11	12	10	15	12	10	9	100	5.01	5
Score	81	96	77	72	50	60	36	20	9	501		
Suitable for Children	17	18	8	10	10	11	10	8	8	100	5.61	1
Score	153	144	56	60	50	44	30	16	8	561		
Advertisement	13	18	10	7	13	13	11	10	5	100	5.48	2
Score	117	144	70	42	65	52	33	20	5	548		

The above table reveals that the respondents have assigned first rank to suitable for children, second rank to interferer advertisement, third rank to health, fourth rank to taste of, fifth rank to package, sixth rank to availability, seventh rank to quantity, eighth rank to price, after ninth rank to quality.

9. Findings:

- ✓ There is a significant relationship between monthly income and Types of organic food products.
- ✓ There no relationship between gender and opinion level of organic food products.
- ✓ Majority of respondents, ranked first to quality of the product

10. Suggestions:

- ✓ The Creation of awareness of organic products is necessary among consumers.
- ✓ Sustained improvement in product features would lead to increase in consumption of organic food products.
- ✓ Allocation of separate shares for organic food products in departmental stores
- ✓ To open more number of organic store
- ✓ Positioning organic food products by influencing consumer beliefs about the benefits they derive on consuming.

11. Conclusion:

India has tremendous potential, largely untapped, for a major breakthrough in organic agriculture. With the effort of government to streamline regulatory mechanisms for improve of organic produce and awareness among local consumer for domestic consumption will pave way for faster development of organic farming. And all give assistant to farmer to grow the organic product. Consumer behaviour is playing the major role while buying not only organic product any product. So the organic shops and product supply is limited but demand for it is more so farmer and all so government are think to improve or increasing production of organic product as well as good packaging, quality and market system it helps to improve the standard of living farmer and all it healthy to environment and all so it helps to government. The seller of the organic product are all so increase. The marketers of organic foods need to be innovative and dynamic in order to complete with the changing purchase behaviour in the Organic food products market among urban residents.

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